

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization"

**Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Evaluator 3 David Reinstein
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ABSTRACT

We organized three evaluations of the paper: "Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization"^[1]. The evaluations are generally extremely positive. However, evaluator 2 expresses some doubts about the novelty of the authors' ("treatment variation aggregation") approach and its practical advantages relative to Bayesian estimators that are more sophisticated than the ones they tested. Evaluator 3 has concerns about the robustness of the assumptions behind the econometric justifications for TVA. They also strongly encourage the authors to provide further software sharing and guidance. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous evaluation 2](#)
3. [Anonymous evaluation 3](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice."

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Anon Evaluator 1 ²	98	5.0
Anon. evaluator 2	95	4.7
Anon. evaluator 3	85	4.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.⁴

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1⁵

This is an absolutely superb paper tackling a hugely important policy question. The authors develop a new econometric approach to aggregating high-dimensional factorial designs in RCTs in order to identify the most effective policies, and apply it to the question of increasing childhood immunization rates. I am thoroughly impressed by every aspect of this paper: the dataset used, the specific treatment arms used, the policy relevance, and the approach to identifying the best policy.

Anonymous evaluator 2

Strengths:

- Introduces a new technique - treatment variant aggregation (TVA) - to answer policy-relevant questions
- Strong theoretical and simulation results grounded in real-world data
- Demonstrates advantages in both selection and estimation of policies by comparing to many alternative estimators
- Application to an urgent, real-world problem

Weaknesses:

- Simulations rely on parameters from a single dataset, limiting generalizability
- Unclear practical advantage of TVA in selecting better policies compared to alternatives
- Bayesian estimators [that are more sophisticated than the ones they tested] could rival or surpass TVA

Anonymous evaluator 3

The method is mostly a clever combination of existing methods; the main contribution is showing [the] consistency and normality of their estimator. These results need not always hold, as they depend on assumptions, and so applicability is not universal. The authors provide guidance by presenting simulations showing that for $n > 3000$, normality seems to hold. The field data reveal no surprise[s], and all the interventions have been tested before. Yet, the paper is strong, and the method will possibly remain relevant despite the recent advances in adaptive experimental design, if the authors provide additional guidance or software.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 ⁶ Anonymous* *		Evaluator 2 Anonymous		Evaluator 3 Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁷	98	(96, 100)	95	(80, 99)	85	(75, 90)	8
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁹	97	(95, 100)	95	(80, 99)	85	(80, 90)	10
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹¹	97	(95, 100)	90	(70, 95)	80	(50, 100)	12
Logic & communication ¹³	96	(93, 100)	90	(70, 95)	80	(50, 100)	14
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁵	96	(92, 100)	90	(70, 95)	70	(25, 80)	16
Real-world relevance ¹⁷	100	(100, 100)	95	(75, 99)	95	(70, 100)	18
Relevance to global priorities ¹⁹	100	(100, 100)	85	(70, 95)	95	(90, 100)	20

** Manager's note: We will not incorporate the ratings from Evaluation 1 into our database/dashboard and analysis, as these show signs of being uncalibrated. In general, we ask our evaluators to take a Bayesian approach to specifying their credible intervals for percentiles and predictions, avoiding degenerate intervals.

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 ²¹ Anonymous*		Evaluator 2 Anonymous		Evaluator 3 Anonymous		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	5.0	(5.0, 5.0)	4.7	(4.0, 5.0)	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)	22
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	5.0	(5.0, 5.0)	4.7	(4.0, 5.0)	4.7	(4.0, 5.0)	23
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 						

Evaluation manager’s discussion

Unjournal process notes

Note on versions: Evaluator 1 and Evaluator 2 considered an earlier (Sept. 2022) version of this paper — the version [on Arxiv here](#). Evaluator 3 considered the June 2024 version [linked here](#). (Evaluators 1 and 2 were

given a chance to adjust their evaluations to the more recent version but declined to do so.)

We shared a set of “bespoke evaluation notes” with the evaluators; these are [linked here](#), and included several specific suggestions for “some key issues and claims to vet”.

Author engagement

We reached out to the authors on April 9 2024 to let them know we were commissioning the evaluation of this paper, asking if they had any particular requests, and asking about any newer or forthcoming versions. On August 10 we shared these evaluations with the authors, which they acknowledged, and declined to respond, noting that the paper had been accepted for publication in the journal *Econometrica*.²⁴

Why we chose this paper

This paper seems to be already having a direct influence on funding/policy in impactful areas. According to the member of our team that suggested this this is “already informing a J-PAL project in India, as well as Suvita.” The discussion of incentives vs reminders seems particularly relevant, it would seem to inform charities like New Incentives.

The methodological question is how to “select the best policy among potential bundles that combine several interventions” and report a credible measure of the impact of this ‘best’ intervention’. This seems valuable for a range of high-impact contexts, from global health interventions to fighting misinformation to promoting effective charitable giving. I expect approaches like TVA (or more Bayesian approaches to this question) to be increasingly used in research and practice.

Issues meriting further evaluation

The “issues and claims” we suggested (in the [aforementioned notes](#)) were partially addressed by the evaluators. Some examples:²⁵

1. “Lasso then prune”/results relying on sparsity assumptions,

As one example, we asked them to consider whether their ‘lasso then prune’ approach was justified. Their statistical justification relies on a sparsity assumption, i.e., in the real world some treatments need to have precisely a zero marginal effect. The third evaluator considered this in part, noting

Treatments that have no effect whatsoever are either "pooled or pruned (pooled with control)".

Scientifically, I am a bit unsure whether this should be allowed; a discussion seems warranted. It is obviously principled and data-driven, but conceptually, it seems wrong to me.

... Whether or not the strong assumptions are likely to be fulfilled in different settings will remain a judgment call.

This issue may merit further, more formal discussion from statisticians and econometricians who work with machine learning/statistical learning.

2. We asked about “scalability of the interventions/economic feasibility for more widespread adoption: Can these strategies be effectively implemented in other regions of India or similar contexts or are there aspects of the context in Haryana state that might affect the generalizability of the results?...” None of the evaluators discussed this issues, nor considered the context (India, immunizations) in detail.
3. The authors report “The most cost-effective policy (information hubs, SMS reminders, no incentives) increases the number of immunizations per dollar by 9.1%” This is not a value/cost measure because it depends on the immunization base rate etc. We’d like to encourage the authors to estimate and report even more relevant Benefit/Cost measures. Future evaluators could offer specific suggestions for this, or estimate these themselves (using the code and data that will presumably be provided along with the final publication in *Econometrica*.)

References

1. Banerjee, A., Chandrasekhar, A. G., Dalpath, S., Duflo, E., Floretta, J., Jackson, M. O., Kannan, H., Loza, F. N., Sankar, A., Schrimpf, A., & Shrestha, M. (2025). Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization. *Econometrica*, 93(4). <https://doi.org/10.3982/ECTA19739>. Working paper: NBER Working Paper No. 28726. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w28726>

Footnotes

1. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. [↵](#)
2. Manager’s note: This evaluation did not involve the level of substantive depth and careful constructive critique that we request. We are posting this with an ‘asterisk’ and we will not incorporate the quantitative ratings into our database. [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
4. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↵](#)
5. [↵](#)
6. Manager’s note: This evaluation did not involve the level of substantive depth and careful constructive critique that we request. We are posting this with an ‘asterisk’ and we will not incorporate the quantitative ratings into our database. [↵](#)
- 7.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

8. Given the fact that each part of the paper in isolation (method; field data) is not in the 15% of best papers in my view (meaning with largest impact), the lower limit of the credible interval is rather low. As the method might have some impact (e.g., if software and more guidance is provided, and if referees are not bothered by the fact that normality is at least quite questionable for sample sizes below 1000), and as the combination (method + field) makes the paper rather unique and quite strong, I have a quite high upper limit for the credible interval. ↵

9.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

10. Even though the method relies on asymptotic and other arguments, and hence, applicability will always be a question, I see the method's relevance as the paper's biggest selling point. I am a bit less sure, however, how relevant it will become in practice. The results of the field data are relevant, but of no particular surprise given my reading of recent literature in the field. ↵

11. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↵

12. As far as I can tell, questionable research practices have been avoided. The robustness to some assumptions is checked, but not for all - in particular - Assumption 5, for example, is quite cryptic. In particular for that, no intuition is given, either. Other assumptions are cleanly explained and justified, even with intuition. ↵

13. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↵

14. This varies a lot throughout the paper. At places, formulas are not explained; the simulation results are not really discussed. E.g., the "r" in Figure 3, Panel A - if a result of the simulations - should be discussed. ↵

15.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

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16. Data and code for replication is not (yet?) made available; this is not unusual until the paper can be accessed via the journal's homepage, once accepted. A pre-registration is available (but it is not prominently mentioned, as this project has not been planned from the beginning). Hence, for the time being (paper is a working paper, not yet accessible via a journal homepage, but apparently accepted), the lower limit of the credible interval must be very low, but I absolutely expect code and data to become available in the future. └
17.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

└

18. Yes, totally. The paper is very relevant for researchers wishing to implement (large-scale as in $N > 1500$) RCTs as well as health practitioners. Assumptions will not be fulfilled in very many settings, though; it is unclear how clustered structures will have to be considered. The authors are to congratulate for making their exposition very accessible in most parts and providing intuition behind their setup for most of the assumptions, yet applicability of the method will remain questionable. └

19. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? └

20. The paper deals with finding the most effective policy methodically, and applies this to an applied question in the health-context of India. └

21. Manager's note: This evaluation did not involve the level of substantive depth and careful constructive critique that we request. We are posting this with an 'asterisk' and we will not incorporate the quantitative ratings into our database. └

22. The paper certainly has the scope and potential for a publication in a journal ranked with 5; quality-wise, I feel that there is a huge overlap of publications in journals ranked with 4 and journals ranked with 5. Without checking the proofs thoroughly, I cannot for sure assess whether it is really made for the very best journals. As assumptions are somewhat strong and not always intuitive, I could imagine that a journal ranked with 5 passes. As the field data is impressive, and the method potentially useful (even though it is

unclear exactly how applicable it is because of the asymptotic arguments and somewhat cryptic assumptions), I understand that a journal ranked with 5 wishes to publish the paper. ↵

23. Publishing in a journal with ranking 5 is random to a high degree in my view compared to publishing in a journal with ranking 4; there is quite some overlap quality-wise. The paper certainly has the scope and potential for a publication in a journal ranked with 5, and being from Stanford must help to push the randomness in the direction of the 5. ↵

24. We generally aim to evaluate economics papers earlier in the process, before acceptance by a top journal. Nonetheless, our evaluations, even 'post-journal-publication' could provide substantial value. What makes a paper 'worthy of *Econometrica*'? What makes a particular paper innovative, credible, or impactful, and who should 'use' the results and methods? Researchers and practitioners (especially those in LMICs and outside elite institutions) can gain from seeing the detailed considerations and painstaking discussions otherwise hidden in the traditional journal review process. ↵

25. As our resources permit, we aim to more concretely follow up this and other our evaluation packages with detailed lists of "Issues meriting further evaluation". We hope this will help guide participants in our nascent "Independent Evaluations" initiative. ↵

References

1. Banerjee, A., Chandrasekhar, A., Dalpath, S., Duflo, E., Floretta, J., Jackson, M., ... Shrestha, M. (2021). *Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w28726> ↵